

Disciplining bodies: Affect in mathematics education

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Identifying children's affective responses towards mathematics and putting efforts to change them are fairly common aspects of modern-day mathematics education. In this paper, I begin to explore how such efforts involve a disciplinary power that aims to maximize the economic utility of bodies and create a specific kind of citizen-worker.

Concerns about the consequences of how children feel about mathematics have often been expressed by researchers and educators alike (Boaler, 2009; McLeod, 1992). As a result, the identification and subsequent modification of affective responses such as beliefs, emotions, and attitudes have become integral to mathematics education. According to the OECD (2016), “teachers should be concerned about students’ attitudes towards mathematics and should take steps to increase students’ positive feelings, self-confidence and interest in mathematics when needed” (p. 77). Today, identifying and changing the way students feel about mathematics is aided by various resources – from teaching practices and strategies to even biosensors for monitoring children’s emotional activity (Williamson, 2016). While these efforts often come across as ‘innocent’ pedagogical practices, “any attempt to promote subjectivity through governing thought is neither benign nor neutral” (Popkewitz, 2004, p. 27). In this paper, I argue that modulating affective responses involves a disciplinary power (Foucault, 1995) that aims to maximize the economic utility of bodies and create a certain kind of citizen-worker. I begin by examining a historically assumed motivation behind efforts to modulate the affective – the desire to increase test scores.

Affect and achievement

Affective responses include “a wide range of beliefs, feelings, and moods that are generally regarded as going beyond the domain of cognition” (McLeod, 1992, p. 576). The association between affective responses and achievement became a naturalized belief due to considerable research in the latter half of the 20th century that posited attitudes and other affective responses as predictors of achievement. These statistically driven studies often established causal relationships between student achievement and a plethora of affective factors such as self-efficacy, confidence, and beliefs (McLeod, 1992). As these relationships became commonsensical, the belief that modulating affective responses will lead to higher test scores took hold.

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However, this belief has been challenged often – due to its lack of insights about the complex and unpredictable ways in which affect and achievement interact (McLeod, 1992), and the uncertainty of whether positive affective responses cause high test scores or the other way around. Still, the modulation of affective responses remains a significant aspect of 21st-century mathematics education. An additional impetus to the prevalence of this aspect has been the growing belief in a connection between mathematics competence and the economic steering of society (Valero, 2018). Thus, through achievement on tests, affective responses get linked to national economic progress. The usage of Likert-type questionnaires on student attitudes and beliefs in comparative global assessments like PISA validates this association.

However, increasing test scores does not seem to be the only motivation anymore for modulating children’s affective responses towards mathematics. Several ‘high-achieving’ countries in the PISA mathematics test such as Korea and Singapore have continued to express concerns over low interest and self-confidence of students in mathematics (OECD, 2016), and made large-scale curricular revisions to improve student attitudes. It becomes imperative then to ask what else drives the efforts to change how students feel about mathematics, beyond mere desires for high test scores. In the next section, I explore the same.

Citizen-workers for modern-day economies

The scientific optimism that began following World War II intensified the popular belief that technological development was the solution to every problem (Skovsmose, 2005). Given the mathematical knowledge required to perform the supposedly essential functions of problem-solving and data-driven decision making in this technological landscape, mathematics has become indispensable. Consequently, mathematical knowledge – seen as a “human right in itself” (Valero, 2018, p. 108) – is now positioned as essential for any nation to advance its economy and technological competence. Anyone with a lack of this knowledge is perceived to be unprepared for ‘an uncertain future’ (Popkewitz, 2004) – a belief that has further amplified the ‘STEM pipeline’.

Following WW II, a notion emerged – of human beings as citizen-workers who had to be trained and equipped with skills for the growth of a nation’s economy (Valero, 2017). With the emergence of mathematical knowledge as vital during the same era, mathematics achievement became a way of assigning an economic value to a human being (Valero, 2018). This idea of human beings as bodies with economic exchange value placed the onus on school mathematics to produce the desired workforce for the technological future. In recent times, the economic potential of individuals is determined not just by their achievement, but through their “ability to apply knowledge to solve problems” and their propensity “to view mathematics as a useful tool that must constantly be sharpened” (National Research Council, 2001, p. 144). In other words, to be economically valuable in today’s technological societies, one needs certain affective qualities too besides their cognitive skills in mathematics.

Due to such labor demands, it becomes necessary to socialize children to possess specific affective responses – turning mathematics classrooms into sites for inculcating these

attitudes and dispositions. With the emergence of cognitive capitalism – in which the production of wealth takes place through not just material production but also through developing the relational, the affective and the cognitive capacities of labor (Moulier Boutang, 2011) – achieving high scores in mathematics tests is not enough anymore. Children now also need to feel a certain way about themselves and mathematics in order to be ‘productive’ as a modern-day citizen-worker. Governing the child’s affective responses, thus, becomes a focus within mathematics education.

Disciplining bodies

Considering such workforce requirements, I argue that the efforts to modulate children’s affective responses are ways of governing their feelings and emotions towards a norm that is valued by modern-day jobs. I use the lenses of *discipline* and *docile bodies* (Foucault, 1995) to elaborate on this. Foucault defined docile bodies as ones “that may be subjected, used, transformed and improved” (1995, p. 136). He saw discipline as a mechanism that ensures that the increased utility of a human body makes it more obedient to commands, and vice versa through a constant subjection of its forces. Discipline produces docile bodies by increasing “the forces of the body (in economic terms of utility) and diminishes the same forces (in political terms of obedience)” (p. 138). Disciplinary techniques initiate “a subtle coercion, of obtaining holds upon it [the body] at the level of the mechanism itself – movements, gestures, attitudes, rapidity: an infinitesimal power over the active body” (p. 137).

To achieve a cognitively and affectively standardized labor force for modern-day technologized societies, mathematics education becomes a site for disciplining bodies. Specifically, with respect to the affective qualities of such bodies, the act of disciplining involves attempts to make all children feel *positively* about mathematics. Those who do not are identified and categorized for subsequent intervention – broadening the notion of what needs *fixing* in mathematics education beyond just the cognitive. A child’s body language, pitch, stress, and other embodied aspects are made available for scrutiny by humans, or in some cases, by technologies such as student sensor bracelets (Williamson, 2016). Such scrutiny marks bodies that need disciplining – whose affective qualities must be standardized for enhancing their economic value. In the case of mathematics, this disciplinary power attempts to ensure specific mental habits, ways of thinking, and self-regulated behaviors that align with a modern-day desire for ‘scientific rationality’ (Popkewitz, 2004). *Negative* affective responses towards mathematics are seen as a threat to progress and development. For example, in the case of the United States, Boaler (2009) states:

Far too many students in America hate math and for many it is a source of anxiety and fear. American students do not achieve well and they do not choose to study mathematics beyond basic courses, a situation that presents serious risks to the future medical, scientific, and technological advancement of society. (p.10)

Seen another way, not feeling a certain way about mathematics diminishes an individual’s mathematical exchange value, and in turn their human capital value (Valero, 2018). Moving away from their earlier motivations of increasing test scores, efforts to

modulate children's affective responses towards mathematics have reorganized under a new goal – the creation of a productive technological workforce.

The aim of this paper is not to evaluate efforts to modulate affect as 'good' or 'bad'. My goal is to draw attention to the mechanisms of discipline entwined in these efforts which render a child's mind and thought governable towards a predetermined norm – one that emerges from the desires of neoliberal economies. Any attempt to standardize minds involves classifications based on idealized criteria and the subsequent exclusions of bodies. As a result, what I challenge through this paper is the standardization of the affective - the commonsensical idea that every child has to feel the same way about mathematics. In the current moment marked by the proliferation of STEM education and its associated exclusionary practices, any efforts that claim innocence in their work to change how students feel about mathematics require scrutiny and critical reflection.

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